

Review

Biological Deterioration and Conservation of Archaeological Wood: A Review

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Abstract: The strength and longevity of wooden materials can be significantly reduced by natural processes such as biological degradation. Various biological agents such as fungi, bacteria, and insects trigger this process by attacking and destroying wood, causing decay, discoloration, and warping. Given the economic importance of wood and its susceptibility to biological degradation, wood preservation techniques need to be addressed by better understanding these biological forces. Beetles and termites are typical wooden insects that can seriously damage wooden structures. Mold formation can cause visual and health problems, and moisture ingress can also cause wood rot. Research to minimize wood biological degradation focuses on understanding the mechanisms of microbial degradation and developing preservation techniques that can halt or slow the decay process. It is important to take a coordinated and planned approach to wood conservation in general, even though there is little information specifically available on the best ways to preserve wood that has been biologically harmed by insects. It is important to consider alternative protection methods based on natural products with little or no toxicity, as well as coordinated and planned efforts for wood conservation in general. The purpose of this article is to provide a general overview of wood biological degradation, including the many biological agents involved, their degradation mechanisms, and methods used to slow or stop the degradation of wood products. The assessment also highlights the economic value of timber and the need for conservation techniques to maintain its longevity and structural integrity.

Keywords: Archaeological wood, Biological degradation, Wood preservation, Polyethylene glycol

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1. Introduction

Wood has been an essential material for human beings for thousands of years. It has been used to make various utilitarian and non-utilitarian objects, as well as basic structural and finishing elements for Furnitures, buildings and other constructions on land and sea [2]. Archaeological wood refers to wood that was used by an extinct human culture and may have been subjected to different types of preservation, such as carbonization, waterlogging, desiccation, and mineralization [1]. Wood is an organic material that is produced from the basic building blocks of carbon dioxide and water

and is recycled back to these building blocks by nature [3]. As a result, wooden artifacts are subject to the recycling chemistries of nature, which can lead to their degradation over time.

Archaeological wood is a valuable source of information about the extinct human culture that used it. The study of archaeological wood can reveal insights into the environment, economy, technology, and social organization of the people who used it [5]. However, archaeological wood requires careful conservation to prevent further deterioration. Wood conservation is defined as a coherent, coordinated, and planned activity of study, prevention, maintenance, and restoration applied to archaeological wood, which may constitute archaeological artifacts partially or in total [4]. Various methods have been developed for the conservation of waterlogged archaeological wood, such as sugar conservation, freeze-drying, and sublimation drying [6][9]. Monitoring the environment and dynamics of wood degradation is fundamental for the in situ preservation of archaeological wooden materials [7]. In recent decades, the science of wood anatomy has evolved to include archaeological and historical wood in its repertoire of documenting and characterizing modern and fossil woods. The increasing use of online wood anatomy databases and atlases has fostered the adoption of an international consensus regarding terminology [8]. Understanding past civilizations: Archaeological wood can provide valuable information about the technology and construction methods used by past civilizations. By studying the growth rings of the wood, researchers can determine the age of the tree and the time period in which the wood was used [9]. The use of certain types of wood can also provide insights into trade and cultural connections between civilizations. Environmental history: The study of archaeological wood can also provide insights into past environmental conditions. For example, tree-ring analysis can provide information about past climate conditions and the impact of natural disasters on forests [9]. Artifact preservation: Preservation of archaeological wood is important to prevent further decay and damage to the artifacts. Exposure to moisture, air, and rough handling can cause disintegration of the wood and damage to any attached artefacts [8]. Future research: Archaeological wood is a non-renewable resource, and once it is lost, the information it holds is lost forever. By preserving archaeological wood, researchers can continue to study and learn from it in the future [5].

The study of the biological degradation of archaeological wood is important for several reasons. Firstly, it helps us to understand how wood deteriorates over time in different environmental conditions, which can help to inform conservation efforts for wooden artifacts and structures [2]. In addition, the slow decay process of waterlogged archaeological wood compared to wood decay above ground, means that the organisms responsible for degradation may differ, and the study of these organisms can provide insights into the unique conditions present in waterlogged environments [3]. Furthermore, studying the biological degradation of wood can provide information about the organisms responsible for decay, including fungi, bacteria, and insects[5,8]. Finally, understanding the mechanisms and rates of decay can provide information about the age and history of wooden artifacts and structures[2].

2. Wood Structure

A fibrous substance called wood is created when secondary xylem generated by the vascular cambium builds up. One of the most common and useful natural materials, it serves as the main supporting tissue in the stems and roots of trees and shrubs. Extremely heterogeneous in both structure and chemical composition, wood exhibits a wide range of physical characteristics, including permeability, capillary behavior, thermal conductivity, and the diffusion of bound water [2]. Based on the type of tree they come from and their unique cell structures, wood is separated into two distinct types: hardwood and softwood [3].

From the nanoscale of the cell walls to the macroscale of the wood stem, it possesses a porous hierarchical structure. The middle lamella, main cell wall, and secondary cell wall are the three layers that make up the stiff cell walls of wood. The primary cell wall is the thin, flexible layer that surrounds the middle lamella, which is a thin layer that holds adjacent cells together. A thick layer made of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin makes up the secondary cell wall. These three layers work together to give wood its strength and stiffness, and the secondary cell wall's orientation of the cellulose microfibrils is what gives wood its anisotropic qualities, which means that they change depending on the direction in which it is loaded [4]. Trees develop annual rings that capture the environment's changing conditions. Rapid spring growth creates "earlywood," which is less thick and made up of big cells with thinner walls, enabling effective water transfer to enable intensive photosynthesis [5]. Tangential and radial orientations experience more dramatic shrinkage than the longitudinal direction as growth rings, or concentric layers, of wood form around a central core (pith) [6].

Figure 1: Hierarchy of wood structure, from meters to nanometers.

source: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/fswoodlab/11439765185>

The anisotropic qualities of wood are caused by the orientation of the cellulose microfibrils in the secondary cell wall, which is characteristic of the hierarchical porous arrangement of cells that gives wood its strength and stiffness. The tree trunk's growth rings, which are developed around the central core, are a reflection of the changing environment. Rapid spring growth results in less dense earlywood with big cells for effective water transfer [1] [6]. Based on the type of tree they come from and their unique cell structures, wood is separated into two distinct types: hardwood and softwood [9].

2.1 Chemical Component

Cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin are the three main chemical elements of wood, making it a complex and adaptable material [7]. The mechanical and chemical qualities of wood are governed by these components, which have various chemical structures and behaviors. In addition to these three essential components, wood also contains extractives, which are organic substances that are present within the wood cells but do not form a part of the cell wall and have a significant role in the preservation and defense of the wood against infections and pests [8].

Figure 2: The figure is showing chemical component of wood

Source: https://coe.northeastern.edu/research/hongli_group/

The majority of a piece of wood, between 40 and 50 percent of its dry weight, is made up of cellulose [9]. It gives wood its mechanical strength and rigidity and is a linear polymer of glucose molecules. It is a kind of carbohydrate polymer that gives the wood structure strength and stiffness [26]. To comprehend the physical and mechanical qualities of wood, it is crucial to grasp the features of wood cellulose. Beta-glycosidic linkages hold the repeating units of glucose molecules that make up the long-chain polymer known as cellulose together. These molecules are organized in linear chains, with hydrogen bonds connecting the chains next to one another [7]. Strength is one of cellulose's key characteristics in wood. For the mechanical integrity of the wood structure, cellulose serves as the wood fibers' principal structural support [5]. Furthermore, cellulose fibers have a high tensile strength, which makes it possible for them to withstand external forces without breaking [7]. Cellulose also plays a critical role in determining the mechanical properties of wood. The orientation and alignment of cellulose fibers in wood influence its mechanical behavior. In softwood, cellulose fibers are primarily aligned in the longitudinal direction, giving it high tensile strength along the grain. In hardwood, cellulose fibers are arranged in multiple directions, contributing to its overall toughness and resistance to deformation [11].

Hemicelluloses are a complex mixture of branched polysaccharides, which make up about 20-30% of the dry weight of wood. They have a lower degree of polymerization than cellulose and are more easily hydrolyzed by acidic or basic conditions.

Hemicelluloses are polysaccharides that coexist with cellulose and lignin in the wood cell walls. They differ from cellulose in their branching and composition, containing a range of monosaccharides, including xylose, mannose, galactose, arabinose, and glucuronic acid. The precise biomechanical roles of hemicelluloses in wood remain elusive; however, they have been found to interact with the cellulose microfibrils and lignin matrix in wood cell walls [10]. Hemicelluloses are significant components of the primary wall and middle lamella or intercellular layer, which are regions rich in pectic material [7]. They are composed of various types of cells, and the fuel properties of wood can be summarized based on

their content of cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin [13]. The complex ultrastructures of wood cell walls, in which cellulose microfibrils are surrounded by a hemicellulose-lignin matrix, significantly affect the pyrolytic reactivity of hemicellulose and cellulose in wood [12]. Moreover, mild pyrolysis is used to improve wood properties such as its decay durability and dimensional stability, with the resulting new properties being the result of chemical modifications of wood cell wall polymers occurring during treatment that confer new properties to wood. Previous studies have shown that the mass loss of wood due to thermodegradation reaction is a consequence of the depolymerization of hemicelluloses, which leads to cross-linking reactions and condensation products [15].

Lignin is a macromolecule found in the cell walls of terrestrial plants, which provides structure and rigidity to the plant [36]. In wood, lignin is one of the three main organic components of the cell wall, along with cellulose and hemicellulose, and constitutes 15-30% of wood [37]. Lignin is a complex hydrocarbon polymer with both aliphatic and aromatic constituents, amorphous, and hydrophobic in nature. Unlike cellulose and hemicellulose, lignin cannot be broken down into monomeric units [32]. The chemical structure of lignin is highly branched and amorphous, and its three-dimensional structure is connected by benzene propane units through various chemical bonds. The type and relative quantity of the bonds between benzene propane units are the main components of lignin's chemical structure. Because of its highly branched, amorphous, and three-dimensional structure, lignin differs from the other two substances (cellulose and hemicelluloses) in wood [31]. The abundance of lignin makes it a valuable resource for various applications. However, relatively few industrial uses for lignin have been found besides as a fuel. A thorough understanding of lignin is desirable for the best utilization of wood [33].

2.2 Environmental Characteristic

The environmental characteristics of wood are crucial in understanding its behavior and properties. Some of the environmental characteristics of wood include wood density, dry shrinkage coefficient, elasticity, strength, and porosity [20]. These characteristics vary depending on the tree species, growth environment, and wood structure [3]. Additionally, wood cells walls consist of an outer primary wall and a multilayered secondary wall, with the secondary wall largely composed of a mixture of cellulose and lignin [10]. Wood density is influenced by various environmental conditions. A study conducted by Wei et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between wood density and environmental variables, such as climate, topography, and soil characteristics. They found that wood density is significantly affected by temperature, precipitation, and soil nutrient availability. Specifically, they observed a positive correlation between wood density and temperature and soil nutrient content, and a negative correlation between wood density and precipitation. Other factors that can affect wood density include altitude, latitude, and tree age [1]. In addition, the water regime, light intensity, and competition for resources can also affect wood density. Wood density plays an important role in the preservation of archaeological wood. When the basic density of the wood is higher than that of non-degraded wood, the Relative Bulk Density (RBD) of the wood takes on a value above 100% [1]. The physical properties of waterlogged archaeological wood, such as basic density and wood substance density, have been used to evaluate the state of preservation of such wood [7][8]. Several techniques have been used to preserve archaeological wood, including radiation curing, freeze-drying, and chemical preservation techniques [4]. The chemical composition of wood, changes brought about by the decay process, biopredators, and museum environments are also important considerations in the preservation of archaeological wood [4]. Relationships between cell-wall composition and cell-wall density have been studied [2], and shape recovery of collapsed archaeological wood ware has been achieved through active alkali-urea treatment [3]. Overall, the density and physical properties of wood are important factors in the preservation of archaeological wood. Various techniques have been used to preserve archaeological wood, and the chemical composition of wood and the decay process are also important considerations in wood preservation. Understanding the environmental characteristics of wood is important for various applications, including construction, furniture-making, and energy

generation. For instance, wood ash mixed with soils has been shown to enhance the durability of soils [7]. Additionally, the adsorptive properties of wood charcoal have been evaluated for potential use in water treatment [8].

3. Biological Deterioration of Wood

Archaeological wood, when exposed to a wet or waterlogged environment, undergoes biological deterioration due to chemical hydrolysis and microbial activity. The cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in the wood break down, making the microvoids in the cell walls larger and the wood more porous [14]. Despite this, under waterlogged and anaerobic conditions, archaeological wood is relatively well protected from biological decomposition compared to degradation in terrestrial environments.

Archaeological wood deterioration caused by microorganisms such as fungi, bacteria, insects, and marine borers [17][16]. The primary cause of deterioration is microbial degradation of cell walls during long-term exposure to natural environments [16]. Insects are the most frequently found animal pests attacking wood, using wood for food, shelter, and breeding [20][7]. Archaeological wood is a valuable cultural property, and its destruction leads to a loss of historical knowledge [17]. Therefore, it is crucial to identify the types of microorganisms that cause deterioration and their morphological and chemical changes [18]. Antimicrobials or preservatives are used to prevent biological deterioration, and natural or synthetic compounds with known and minimal toxicological effects on mammals and the environment are preferred [25]. Living organisms, such as insects, fungi, and bacteria, break down the organic components of wood, leading to its decay and eventual loss of structural integrity.

Insects and fungi are the two main biological agents that cause wood deterioration, and they are found to be the most important and most frequently found animal pests attacking wood [2][3]. Shipworms (Teredinidae and Xylaphaginae), which belong to the group of bivalves, are known as the most aggressive degraders of wood in oxygenated and saline waters worldwide [4]. Insects can be divided into dry-wood pests and damp (green)-wood pests, and they use wood for food, shelter, and breeding [5]. is found principally in the form of insects and fungi, and it is essential to conserve wood through a better understanding of these biological agencies [6][7].

Wood is decomposed by a variety of biological agents, including fungi, bacteria, and insects. Fungi colonize wood and degrade cell wall components to form brown, soft, or white rot, while bacteria consume the starches stored in ray cells which generally affects only water-saturated wood [8][10]. Bacteria are one of the primary degraders of wood and wooden structures of historical and cultural importance, particularly those recovered from oxygen-deficient environments [3].

Bacterial deterioration can result in the deterioration of the lignocellulose structure of wood, with bacteria also able to attack the pit membranes in tracheid and ray parenchyma, resulting in a severe impact on wood quality [7]. Information on the state of cell walls at the micro- and ultrastructural levels can be useful in developing and fine-tuning restoration methods for wood structures affected by bacterial deterioration [3].

Additionally, the physiology of wood-damaging bacteria is influenced by various factors such as trophic, abiotic, biological, and anthropogenic factors present in their environment of activity [8].

3.1 Insect

Wood-destroying and xylophagous insects have a worldwide distribution in both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, and the most common wood-destroying insects belong to the orders Coleoptera (beetles) and Isoptera (termites) [26]. These insects are referred to as wood-eating (xylophagous) insects and are considered wood pests in terrestrial environments [35]. Different insect pests with different damage potential could be causing biodegradation to wood and

wooden products in different areas. Infestation by insect pests usually starts in the raw material at the felling site and may continue in the timber depot and thereafter in the finished product or even after being passed on to the consumer [34].

Beetle's larvae. Source:theguardian.com

Deathwatch beetle Source:westernexterminator.com/

Termites. Source:pestworldforkids.org/

Termites. Source: https:lawnlove.com

Figure 3: Showing Insects wood destroying insect attacking wood

Source: google.com

Source: google.com

Figure 4: Shows the impact of insect attack on wooden artifacts

The Cerambycidae family is one of the economically most important wood-boring insects, and the microclimate of tree trunks, canopy, and branches is a significant factor for the normal growth and development of this pest. Termites manipulate the moisture content of wood to maximize foraging resources [6]. Globally, the net effect of insects on wood decomposition may result in a carbon flux of $3.2 \pm 0.9 \text{ Pg C yr}^{-1}$, which represents 29% of the total carbon released from deadwood [4]. The biological degradation of wood by insects can cause structural changes to the wood, which affects various physical and mechanical properties of damaged wood [7].

Insects play a significant role in the biological deterioration of wood, and the most common wood-destroying insects belong to the orders Coleoptera and Isoptera. Different insect pests with varying damage potential could be causing biodegradation to wood and wooden products in different areas. The Cerambycidae family is one of the economically most important wood-boring insects, and termites manipulate the moisture content of wood to maximize foraging resources. The biological degradation of wood by insects can cause structural changes to the wood, affecting various physical and mechanical properties of damaged wood.

3.2 Fungi

Fungi play an important role in the biological deterioration of wood [1]. They are responsible for the majority of wood decay and can cause significant damage to wooden structures and cultural artifacts [2]. Fungi are categorized into three types based on the type of wood decay they cause: brown rot, white rot, and soft rot [3]. Brown rot fungi cause the wood to become brown, brittle, and breakable, while white rot fungi cause the wood to become lighter in color and fibrous. Soft rot fungi cause the wood to lose strength and become cracked and brittle [3].

White rot decay on wood

Source:stock.adobe.com

Brown rot decay on wood

Source:www.mdpi.com

Soft rot decay on wood

Source: www.researchgate.net

Figure 5: Showing the 3 kinds of fungal deterioration of wood

Fungi are able to break down the lignin and cellulose components of wood through the secretion of enzymes such as laccase, manganese peroxidase, and lignin peroxidase [4]. Fungi can also produce acids that lower the pH of the wood, making it more susceptible to decay [3]. Overall, fungi are a major contributor to the biological deterioration of wood, and understanding their role in wood decay is important for the preservation of wooden structures and cultural artifacts [2][4]. The growth of fungi that cause the biological deterioration of wood can be influenced by a variety of factors, including moisture content, temperature, pH, and the presence of nutrients [5]. Moisture content is the most critical factor, as it is essential for the growth and metabolism of fungi. In general, fungi thrive in environments with high relative humidity and moisture levels above 20% [7]. The optimum temperature for fungal growth typically ranges from 20 to 35°C, with some species being able to grow at temperatures as low as 4°C and as high as 45°C [5]. The pH of the wood also plays a role in fungal growth, with most fungi preferring a slightly acidic environment (pH 5.0 to 6.5) [5]. Finally, the presence of nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, is necessary for fungal growth and proliferation [7].

3.3 Bacteria

Bacteria play a significant role in the biological deterioration of wood. They act as a lignocellulose structure deteriorator, and they are able to attack the pit membranes in tracheid and ray parenchyma, resulting in very rapid degradation of wood [8]. Detailed information on the state of cell walls at the micro- and ultrastructural levels can be useful in developing and fine-tuning restoration methods [4]. Wood-degrading bacteria (WDB) are ubiquitous in nature and are present in terrestrial and aquatic environments. WDB have evolved mechanisms and adaptations that enable them to effectively degrade wood. WDB use extracellular enzymes, such as cellulases and hemicellulases, to depolymerize wood polymers, and then utilize the resulting monomers for energy and biosynthesis [10].

Figure 6: SEM images of ship hull sections demonstrating severe bacterial deterioration of the wood cells. Waterlogged wood weakens as a result of bacterial attack. Due to the compromised integrity of the cell walls, the wood cells in the bottom photo are deformed and have collapsed.

Source: forestpathology.cfans.umn.edu

In archaeological wood, bacterial deterioration acts as a lignocellulose structure deteriorator, resulting in degradation of wood. The bacterial attack on wood results in structural changes that can affect various physical and mechanical properties of damaged wood [5]. Bacteria require moisture to thrive and cause wood decay. Therefore, controlling the moisture content of wood is an effective way to minimize bacterial activity. This can be achieved by proper storage, ventilation, and avoiding direct contact with soil [4]. There is a growing interest in understanding the impact of bacteria on wood deterioration and finding ways to minimize it. Bacterial degradation of wood is a complex process influenced by various factors such as environmental conditions, wood properties, and the presence of other organisms like fungi [4].

3.4 Summary

The biological deterioration of wood in archaeological sites. The cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in the wood break down due to microbial activity and chemical hydrolysis. Insects and fungi are the primary agents that cause wood deterioration, with insects belonging to the orders Coleoptera (beetles) and Isoptera (termites). Fungi colonize wood and degrade cell wall components to form brown, soft, or white rot, while bacteria consume the starches stored in ray cells. The Cerambycidae family is one of the economically most important wood-boring insects, and termites manipulate the moisture content of wood to maximize foraging resources. Wood can be conserved by identifying the types of microorganisms that cause deterioration and their morphological and chemical changes. Antimicrobials or preservatives are used to prevent biological deterioration, and natural or synthetic compounds with known and minimal toxicological effects on mammals and the environment are preferred.

4. Conservation of biologically degraded wood

4.1 Characteristics of biologically degraded wood

Biologically degraded wood is a complex material that can be attacked and degraded by a wide range of biological organisms. Waterlogged archaeological wood, for example, is degraded very slowly compared to wood decay above ground due to the special environmental conditions below ground that result in a prolonged decay process under extremely low oxygen concentration that only allows bacterial degradation of wood. The so-called erosion bacteria are described and studied in [30]. One study has investigated the use of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) techniques to identify when degradation of wood occurs in the structure and the performance characteristics that remain in the structure. These techniques may be useful for identifying decay patterns and types in biologically degraded wood [28][27]. Cell wall degradation patterns of buried and waterlogged wooden objects of cultural heritage were reviewed in a mini review article, which also included a brief background on wood structure. The article mentioned different types of microbial decay and associated patterns of cell wall degradation commonly found in biologically degraded wood objects of cultural heritage [16]. One study focused on the comparison of the durability of thermally modified (TM) and untreated (UT) mini-stakes exposed to in-ground contact by modulus of elasticity (MOE) and mass loss with decay type using microscopy. Results showed a strong correlation between MOE and soft rot decay for UT stakes over a 30-month exposure period. For TM stakes, the correlation between MOE and decay rate (soft rot/bacteria) was not as strong [29]. The application of confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) in the studies of biological materials is rapidly expanding, including forestry and wood science studies, due to its opportunity to produce sharp, high-resolution images through optical sectioning and computer-assisted 3-D reconstruction [5]. A study used an alkali treatment and one of the wood-degrading fungi to mimic degraded archaeological wood and obtain larger amounts of similarly degraded wood specimens [7].

Figure 7: Showing (CLSM) which is used to check the level of decay and type.

Source: Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Jena

4.2 Conservation strategy

It is important to understand the causes of wood degradation. Biological degradation of wood can be caused by fungi, insects, and bacteria [6]. Therefore, the conservation methods will depend on the specific cause of degradation.

For example, for fungal decay, some conservation methods include treating the wood with a fungicide, reducing moisture content, and improving ventilation [6]. For insect attack, fumigation, and using insecticides can be effective [6]. To conserve archaeological wood from fungal decay, several strategies can be employed. One approach is to modify the cell wall of the wood to keep the moisture content below favorable conditions for decay organisms [10]. Another approach is to use chemical treatments that can prevent fungal growth and decay [1]. However, the use of chemical treatments may have adverse effects on the environment and human health, and it may also affect the authenticity of the wooden heritage [5].

Furthermore, it is also essential to consider the type of wood that is being conserved. Different types of wood require different conservation methods based on their properties and characteristics. For instance, hardwoods are more resistant to decay than softwoods, and their conservation methods will differ [6]. To conserve biologically degraded wood, it is crucial to identify the cause of degradation and select appropriate conservation methods based on the type of wood. This could involve treating the wood with a fungicide, reducing moisture content, improving ventilation, fumigating, or using insecticides. Further research may be necessary to determine the most effective approach for a specific situation.

4.3 Conservation materials

The use of consolidants in wood conservation. Consolidants are materials that are applied to deteriorated wood to strengthen it and prevent further decay. that consolidants can be classified into two categories: film-forming and penetrating. Film-forming consolidants create a surface layer that covers the wood and protects it from environmental factors. Penetrating consolidants, on the other hand, seep into the wood and bind the deteriorated fibers together. The authors caution that the use of consolidants requires careful consideration of the type of wood and the degree of deterioration, as well as the long-term effects of the consolidant on the object. The use of polyethylene glycol (PEG) in the conservation of waterlogged wood. PEG is a synthetic polymer that is used as a consolidant because it can replace the water in the wood cells without causing shrinkage or distortion. The use of PEG requires careful monitoring of the temperature and humidity during the treatment process to ensure that the PEG is absorbed evenly throughout the wood. [20]

PEG is the most commonly used consolidant for waterlogged wood, as it penetrates the wood fibers and replaces the water, providing support and preventing further degradation [19][22][24]. Alum is another consolidant that has been used in the past, but it is less effective than PEG and can cause damage to the wood if not used properly [21]. Trehalose and feather keratin have also been used as alternative consolidants, with promising results in terms of dimensional stability [22].

Other materials that are commonly used in the conservation of waterlogged wood include cellulose ether gels as thickening agents for retaining solvents on surfaces, and epoxy resin and UV-curing methacrylates for the restoration of ceramics and glass [24]. It is important to note that the choice of materials used in the conservation process may vary depending on the type of wood being treated and the specific conditions of the site [23][21].

Figure 8: Showing archaeological wood

Source: qaronline.org

Figure 9: Showing artifacts been absorb in PEG and dryer where the wooden artifacts will be use to dry them

Source: qaronline.org

Importance of documentation and monitoring in wood conservation. the need for comprehensive documentation of the artifact's condition, the conservation methods used, and the materials used in conservation. Regular monitoring is also necessary to detect any changes in the artifact's condition and ensure that the conservation efforts are effective in preventing further deterioration.

various steps involved in the conservation of waterlogged wood, including desalination, drying, and consolidation. Desalination is necessary because the salt in the water can cause further damage to the wood. Drying must be done slowly and carefully to prevent the wood from warping or cracking. Consolidation is essential to strengthen the wood and prevent it from collapsing [20]

4.4 Summary

Biological degradation of wood leads to the loss of hemicelluloses and celluloses and lignin modification. Different types of microbial decay and associated patterns of cell wall degradation commonly found in biologically degraded wood objects of cultural heritage. The conservation methods for biologically degraded wood depend on the specific cause of degradation, and different types of wood require different conservation methods. Consolidants are materials that are applied to deteriorated wood to strengthen it and prevent further decay, and they can be classified into two categories: film-forming and penetrating. PEG is the most commonly used consolidant for waterlogged wood, as it penetrates the wood fibers and replaces the water, providing support and preventing further degradation. Other materials that are commonly used in the conservation of wood include waxes, resins, and adhesives.

To conserve biologically degraded wood, it is crucial to identify the cause of degradation and select appropriate conservation methods based on the type of wood. This could involve treating the wood with a fungicide, reducing moisture content, improving ventilation, fumigating, or using insecticides. Further research and expert advice may be necessary to determine the most effective approach for a specific situation. While there is limited information available specifically on the most effective way to conserve wood that has been degraded by insects, it is important to consider alternative protection methods based on natural products with little or no toxicity, as well as coordinated and planned efforts for wood conservation in general.

In summary, to conserve biologically degraded wood, it is crucial to identify the cause of degradation and select appropriate conservation methods based on the type of wood. This could involve treating the wood with a fungicide, reducing moisture content, improving ventilation, fumigating, or using insecticides. Further research and expert advice may be necessary to determine the most effective approach for a specific situation.

5. Conclusion

The biological deterioration of wood in archaeological sites. The cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in the wood break down due to microbial activity and chemical hydrolysis. Insects and fungi are the primary agents that cause wood deterioration, with insects belonging to the orders Coleoptera (beetles) and Isoptera (termites). Fungi colonize wood and degrade cell wall components to form brown, soft, or white rot, while bacteria consume the starches stored in ray cells. The Cerambycidae family is one of the economically most important wood-boring insects, and termites manipulate the moisture content of wood to maximize foraging resources. Wood can be conserved by identifying the types of microorganisms that cause deterioration and their morphological and chemical changes. Antimicrobials or preservatives are used to prevent biological deterioration, and natural or synthetic compounds with known and minimal toxicological effects on mammals and the environment are preferred. Further research may be necessary to determine the most effective approach for a specific situation.

References

- [1] Oliveira, G. M. V., de Mello, J. M., de Mello, C. R., Scolforo, J. R. S., Miguel, E. P., & Monteiro, T. C. (2021). Behavior of wood basic density according to environmental variables. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 33(2), 497–505. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-021-01372-2>
- [2] Siau, John Finn. "Wood Structure and Chemical Composition." *Transport Processes in Wood*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1984, pp. 35–72. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/978-3-642-69213-0_2.
- [3] "Wood - an Introduction to Its Structure, Properties, and Uses." *Explain That Stuff*, 4 Sept. 2010, www.explain-thatstuff.com/wood.html.
- [4] Chen, Chaoji, et al. "Structure–property–function Relationships of Natural and Engineered Wood - Nature Reviews Materials." *Nature*, 4 May 2020, doi:10.1038/s41578-020-0195-z.
- [5] "The Wood From the Trees: The Use of Timber in Construction." *The Wood From the Trees: The Use of Timber in Construction - ScienceDirect*, 13 Oct. 2016, doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.09.107.
- [6] "Properties of Wood and Structural Wood Products." https://www.dot.state.mn.us/bridge/pdf/insp/USFS-TimberBridgeManual/em7700_8_chapter03.pdf, Department of Transportation Minnesota, 1 Apr. 2009, www.dot.state.mn.us/bridge/pdf/insp/USFS-TimberBridgeManual/em7700_8_chapter03.pdf.
- [7] Côté, Wilfred A. "Chemical Composition of Wood." *Principles of Wood Science and Technology*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1968, pp. 55–78. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/978-3-642-87928-9_2.
- [8] "Wood - Chemical Products." *Encyclopedia Britannica*, www.britannica.com/science/wood-plant-tissue.
- [9] PETERSEN, ROGER C. "The Chemical Composition of Wood." *Advances in Chemistry*, American Chemical Society, May 1984, pp. 57–126. *Crossref*, doi:10.1021/ba-1984-0207.ch002.

- [10] Berglund, Jennie, et al. "Wood Hemicelluloses Exert Distinct Biomechanical Contributions to Cellulose Fibrillar Networks." *Nature Communications*, vol. 11, no. 1, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, Sept. 2020. *Crossref*, doi:10.1038/s41467-020-18390-z.
- [11] Salmén, Lennart. "Wood Morphology and Properties From Molecular Perspectives." *Annals of Forest Science*, vol. 72, no. 6, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, July 2014, pp. 679–84. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/s13595-014-0403-3.
- [12] Wang, Jiawei, et al. "Thermal Reactivity of Hemicellulose and Cellulose in Cedar and Beech Wood Cell Walls." *Journal of Wood Science*, vol. 66, no. 1, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, May 2020. *Crossref*, doi:10.1186/s10086-020-01888-x.
- [13] Demirbas, T., and C. Demirbas. "Fuel Properties of Wood Species." *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, vol. 31, no. 16, Informa UK Limited, Aug. 2009, pp. 1464–72. *Crossref*, doi:10.1080/15567030802093153.
- [14] Nguyen, Thanh Duc, et al. "Shrinkage and Swelling Behavior of Archaeological Waterlogged Wood Preserved With Slightly Crosslinked Sodium Polyacrylate." *Journal of Wood Science*, vol. 64, no. 3, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, Jan. 2018, pp. 294–300. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/s10086-018-1696-x.
- [15] Candelier, Kévin, et al. "Comparison of Mechanical Properties of Heat Treated Beech Wood Cured Under Nitrogen or Vacuum." *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, vol. 98, no. 9, Elsevier BV, Sept. 2013, pp. 1762–65. *Crossref*, doi:10.1016/j.polymerdegradstab.2013.05.026.
- [16] Singh, Adya P. "A Review of Microbial Decay Types Found in Wooden Objects of Cultural Heritage Recovered From Buried and Waterlogged Environments." *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, vol. 13, no. 3, Elsevier BV, Sept. 2012, pp. S16–20. *Crossref*, doi:10.1016/j.culher.2012.04.002.
- [17] Blanchette, Robert A. "A Review of Microbial Deterioration Found in Archaeological Wood From Different Environments." *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*, vol. 46, no. 3, Elsevier BV, Oct. 2000, pp. 189–204. *Crossref*, doi:10.1016/s0964-8305(00)00077-9.
- [18] Blanchette, Robert A., et al. "Biological Degradation of Wood." *Archaeological Wood*, American Chemical Society, May 1989, pp. 141–74. *Crossref*, doi:10.1021/ba-1990-0225.ch006.
- [19] Broda, Magdalena, and Callum A. S. Hill. "Conservation of Waterlogged Wood—Past, Present and Future Perspectives." *Forests*, vol. 12, no. 9, MDPI AG, Sept. 2021, p. 1193. *Crossref*, doi:10.3390/f12091193.
- [20] Unger, Achim, et al. "Biological Deterioration of Wood." *Conservation of Wood Artifacts*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2001, pp. 51–141. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/978-3-662-06398-9_6.
- [21] Broda, Magdalena, and Callum A. S. Hill. "Conservation of Waterlogged Wood—Past, Present and Future Perspectives." *Forests*, vol. 12, no. 9, MDPI AG, Sept. 2021, p. 1193. *Crossref*, doi:10.3390/f12091193.
- [22] Nguyen, Thanh Duc, et al. "Evaluation of Chemical Treatments on Dimensional Stabilization of Archeological Waterlogged Hardwoods Obtained From the Thang Long Imperial Citadel Site, Vietnam." *Journal of Wood Science*, vol. 64, no. 4, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, Apr. 2018, pp. 436–43. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/s10086-018-1719-7.
- [23] "Conservation and Restoration of Waterlogged Wood - Wikipedia." *Conservation and Restoration of Waterlogged Wood - Wikipedia*, 1 June 2022, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Conservation_and_restoration_of_waterlogged_wood.
- [24] Oddy, W. A. "Chemistry in the Conservation of Archaeological Materials." *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 143, no. 1, Elsevier BV, Mar. 1994, pp. 121–26. *Crossref*, doi:10.1016/0048-9697(94)90538-x.
- [25] "Biological Deterioration - an Overview | ScienceDirect Topics." *Biological Deterioration - an Overview | ScienceDirect Topics*, doi:10.1016/B978-0-08-101872-9.00004-2.
- [26] Pournou, Anastasia. "Wood Deterioration by Insects." *Biodeterioration of Wooden Cultural Heritage*, Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 425–526. *Crossref*, doi:10.1007/978-3-030-46504-9_7.

- [27] Ross, K., et al. "Technique for Nondestructive Evaluation of Biologically Degraded Wood | Semantic Scholar." *Technique for Nondestructive Evaluation of Biologically Degraded Wood* | *Semantic Scholar*, 1 Jan. 1998, www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Technique-for-nondestructive-evaluation-of-degraded-Ross-Degroot/dd24208414d9bbe7e69ae59c2b823dd761bf70ea.
- [28] Ross, Robert J., et al. "Nondestructive Evaluation of Biologically Degraded Wood." *Nondestructive Evaluation of Biologically Degraded Wood* | *SpringerLink*, doi:10.1007/978-1-4615-2574-5_69.
- [29] Råberg, U., et al. "LOSS OF STRENGTH IN BIOLOGICALLY DEGRADED THERMALLY MODIFIED WOOD | Semantic Scholar." *LOSS OF STRENGTH IN BIOLOGICALLY DEGRADED THERMALLY MODIFIED WOOD* | *Semantic Scholar*, 1 Jan. 2017,
- [30] Gjelstrup Björdal, Charlotte. "Microbial Degradation of Waterlogged Archaeological Wood." *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, vol. 13, no. 3, Elsevier BV, Sept. 2012, pp. S118–22. *Crossref*, doi:10.1016/j.culher.2012.02.003.